

Use of CRISPR-Cas9 Technology in Agriculture: an Overview

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With the world's population predicted to exceed 9 billion people by 2050, modern agriculture will confront enormous difficulties, demanding bigger yields and higher quality products while using fewer inputs (Khatodia et al., 2016). Traditional breeding is presently the most extensively used method of plant improvement, although it is time-consuming and takes several years to develop from the first survey of phenotypes and genotypes to the first crosses into commercial cultivars. In order to accommodate the world's rising population, the food industry has set a deadline of 2050 for developing and extending the food supply chain. The food sector is now in a position to produce some of the most exciting developments since the Green Revolution, thanks to the introduction of CRISPRs and CRISPR (Cas) proteins (Huang et al., 2017).

CRISPR –Cas (clustered regularly interspaced short palindromic repeats) is an adaptive phage immunity mechanism discovered in archaea and bacteria. Because CRISPR–Cas9 and other CRISPR–Cas systems rely on DNA–RNA recognition and binding for sequence-specific nucleic acid cleavage, double-strand breaks at any desired target site may be readily induced at low cost (Mali et al., 2013). CRISPR–Cas has been used to modify the genomes of a number of crop species, adding valuable agricultural features into several of them (Zhang et al., 2020). Because of their ability to induce exact nucleotide alterations, the recently discovered precision CRISPR–Cas technologies, in particular, promise to have a significant influence on agriculture. The methodology of its work is represented in Fig 1.

Fig 1: CRISPR Cas9 working methodology (Es et al., 2019)

Application of CRISPR Cas9 technology in crop improvement

Unlike traditional breeding methods, CRISPR–Cas technology allows scientists to quickly create optimal germplasms by removing undesirable genetic elements or inserting gain-of-function mutations through precise genome editing. As shown in Fig 2, CRISPR–Cas has improved a variety of agricultural attributes, including yield, quality, disease resistance, and herbicide resistance.

Fig 2: Areas of application of CRISPR Cas9 technology in crop improvement (Es et al., 2019)

Increasing yield- Manipulation of cytokinin homeostasis is a realistic technique to boost grain production among the many factors impacting yield. In a range of climatic conditions, editing the C terminus of *Oryza sativa* *LOGL5*, which encodes a cytokinin-activation enzyme in rice, increased crop productivity (Wang et al., 2020). Similarly, the cytokinin oxidase/dehydrogenase (CKX) gene, which catalyses cytokinin breakdown, was knocked out to create high-yield wheat genotypes (Zhang et al., 2019). Rice variants with increased tiller numbers and yields while retaining grain quality were created by knocking out the gene that encodes amino acid permease 3, which is important in nutrient partitioning (Lu et al., 2018). CRISPR–Cas-mediated editing of additional genes, such as *O. sativa* *PIN5b* (controlling panicle size), *O. sativa* *GS3* (regulating grain size) (Zeng et al., 2019), *Triticum aestivum* *GW2* (Zhang et al., 2018), *O. sativa* *GW2* (Zhou et al., 2019) and *O. sativa* *GW5* (regulating grain weight) (Liu et al., 2017), has also resulted in higher-yielding crop plants.

Improving quality- Low-amylose grain is great for eating and cooking, and it's used in a variety of sectors including textiles and adhesives. Due to the importance of granule-bound starch synthase 1 (GBSS1) in amylose biosynthesis, waxy maize varieties were created in 12 elite inbred lines by disrupting GBSS1 with CRISPR–Cas9 (Gao et al., 2020), and rice lines with a continuum of low amylose contents were created by changing the amino acid sequence of GBSS1 with a cytosine base editor (CBE) (Xu et al., 2020). Gluten proteins contained in wheat grains can lead to coeliac disease in those who are susceptible. Gluten proteins are encoded by almost 100 loci in the wheat genome, hence typical breeding approaches will not be able to significantly reduce gluten levels. Low-gluten wheat lines with up to 85% lower immunoreactivity have been developed using CRISPR–Cas to target the conserved area of gluten genes (Sánchez-León et al., 2018). CRISPR–Cas has also made it easier to develop high-quality crops with higher levels of carotenoid (Dong et al., 2020) and -aminobutyric acid (Li et al., 2018), lower levels of phytic acid (Khan et al., 2019), and higher levels of oleic acid (Do et al., 2019).

Disease resistance- Rice lines with broad-spectrum resistance to *X. oryzae* pv. *oryzae* were developed using CRISPR–Cas9 to modify the promoter region of *O. sativa* *SWEET11*, *O. sativa* *SWEET13*, and *O. sativa* *SWEET14* (Xu et al., 2019; Oliva et al., 2019). Citrus resistance to *Xanthomonas citri* subsp. *citri* can also be conferred by targeting the *Citrus X sinensis* *LOB1* promoter region (Peng et al., 2017). *EDR1* is a MAPK kinase that reduces wheat defence responses to powdery mildew; CRISPR–Cas mutation of three wheat homologues of *EDR1* resulted in plants with better resistance to *B. graminis* f. sp *Tritici* (Zhang et al., 2017). CRISPR–Cas to target *Solanum lycopersicum* *MLO1* conferred tolerance to powdery mildew-causing *Oidiumneo lycopersici* in tomato (Nekrasov et al., 2017), and simultaneous mutation of all *three mildew-resistance locus O* (*MLO*) homologues resulted in a wheat variety with broad-spectrum powdery mildew resistance (Wang et al., 2014).

Herbicide resistance- Editing herbicide-targeted genes to give endogenous resistance via CRISPR–Cas is intriguing in comparison to typical transgenic approaches that introduce foreign herbicide-resistant genes into crops, such as *bar*, which encodes phosphinothricin N-acetyltransferase. Acetolactate synthase (ALS), a crucial enzyme in the production of branched-chain amino acids, is targeted by sulfonylurea and imidazolinone herbicides. Specific amino acid changes in the ALS gene have been shown to cause herbicide tolerance in studies of naturally occurring point mutations in the ALS gene (Powles et al., 2010). As a result of employing CBEs to introduce particular base transitions into *O. sativa* *ALS*, herbicide resistance was conferred to rice while ALS activity was maintained (Kuang et al., 2020). Similar techniques were employed in other species, like as in ALS, where herbicide tolerance was conferred by introducing specific mutations by HDR (Sun et al., 2016). Furthermore, it has been found that altering *EPSPS* (Hummel et al., 2018), *PPO* (de Pater et al., 2018), *TubA2* (Liu et al., 2021) and *SF3B1* (Butt et al., 2019) confers resistance to glyphosate, butafenacil, trifluralin, and herbexidiene (GEX1A) respectively.

Conclusion

Over the last five years, several plant systems have been widely employed to undertake functional research, battle biotic and abiotic challenges, and improve other vital agricultural characteristics. While various improvements to this technology will improve target quality, the majority of the work done thus far is preliminary. CRISPR/Cas9-based genome editing, on the other hand, will gain popularity and become a vital tool for appropriate plant editing, assisting in the achievement of the zero-hunger objective and ensuring food security for the expanding human population.

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